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GIS Based Assessment of Ground Water Potential in Tlawng Watershed, Mizoram

- Zoramkhuma

Abstract : Ground water is often withdrawn for different purpose. It is important source to meet the water requirements of various sectors including irrigation, domestic and industries. Similar to other parts of Mizoram, groundwater is an important source of water for agricultural and domestic uses in Tlawng watershed. Its physical structure narrow, with a small area and a high-population density create another hindrance in ground water management. The elevation of the terrain of basins is great and steep, meaning that most precipitation becomes runoff and drains directly to the main channel very quickly. It result water resources and water demand are unevenly distributed spatially and temporally. Assessment of ground water potential zones is prerequisite in Tlawng watershed. Shortage has recently become an important issue in Tlawng watershed area; due to more than 50 percent (Census, 2011) of the Mizoram populations are settled in Tlawng watershed. Assessment of ground water is needed to regulate the usage of water resources in order to solve the problem of water shortages. In this study Remote Sensing data and GIS and techniques will be deployed for assessment of ground water potential zonation. The present study proved geospatial technology Remote Sensing data and GIS techniques are suitable for assessment of ground water potential in Tlawng watershed. For ground water potential assessment thematic layers like Slope, Relative Relief, Lithology, Geological Structure, Drainage Density, Vegetation Cover, Land Use/Land Cover and Rainfall data are integrated using Weighted Overlay technique (Multi Criteria Decision Making) . The study reveals that uneven distribution of ground water potential zones over the study areas is mainly determined by the lithology, geological structure, slope and rainfall intensity. Vast areas of valley fills, flood plain and low laying areas have more advantages of ground water potential due to the lithology, slope and proximity of surface water helps ground water recharge. Generally the elevated areas and ridges line belongs to poor ground water potential, due to the rapid runoff and limited vegetation cover.

Keywords : Remote Sensing, GIS, Assessment of ground water, Ground water potential, Ground water potential zones, Tlawng watershed.

Introduction :

Groundwater is one of the most valuable natural resources, and supports human health, economic development and ecological diversity (Hutti & Nijagunappa, 2011). No doubt human development is hinge on availability of ground water and

surface water resources. Groundwater is a dynamic and replenishing natural resource (Nagarajan & Singh, 1997). Anthropogenic activities affect the infiltration and runoff characteristics of the land surface, which affects ground water

Zoramkhuma is a Research Scholar in the Department of Geography & Resource Management, Mizoram University, Aizawl.

recharge and quality (Scanlon et al., 2005; Vijay et al., 2011,). Physical factors affect the occurrence and movement of groundwater in a region including topography, lithology, lineament, slope, relief and drainage. All of these factors either directly or indirectly interrelate with ground water resource. A ground water resource is often critical and no single comprehensive technique is yet identified which is capable of estimating accurate ground water assessment. In recent years, integration Remote Sensing data provides spatial and temporal information which is more reliable and conducive for ground water assessment. Progress of Geographic Information System opened a new platform of spatial data integration and reliable tools for natural resource management which is more useful for ground water assessment (Shankar & Mohan, 2006).

The complexities of the processes governing occurrence and movement of ground water make the problem of ground water assessment (GWREM, 2009).The topography and physiographic expression of the Mizoram is imparted by approximately N-S trending steep, mostly anticlinal, parallel to sub-parallel hill ranges and narrow adjoining synclinal valleys with series of parallel hummocks or topographic highs (Geological Survey of India, 2011). The amount of rainfall is comparatively high during monsoon

season, shortage of water is often experienced in the post-monsoon season and winter (Dry Season), as most of the water available is lost to surface runoff. The uneven topographic and geological conditions over the space and unequal distribution of rainfall, anthropogenic activity over time and space bring emphasis on assessment of groundwater potential zones in Tlawng watershed of Mizoram. The continuous development of the economy has led to an increase in water consumption, and has consequently resulted in shortages of water resource.

Study Area :

The study area is located between 92°27'28"E to 92°48'E Longitude and 22°49'57"N to 24°14'41"N Latitude. Tlawng watershed occupies the central and western part of Mizoram, parts of Lunglei, Serchhip, Aizawl, Kolasib and Mamit districts are in Tlawng watershed. This is one of the longest and largest rivers in Mizoram. The geographical areas of Tlawng watershed is 2792.6 sq. kms. It holds more than 60 per cent of urban population of Mizoram (Census, 2011). This river originated at an elevation of 1146 m from Mean Sea Level from the southern part of Zobawk, Lunglei district and flows towards north direction and discharges into Barrak river in Cachar district of Assam. The

geology, soil texture, characteristics and climate are typically uniform over the watershed including the distribution pattern. The lithology in the area is developed from tertiary deposits belonging to Surma group highs (GSI, 2011).

The terrain is highly mountainous in the south compared to north. The mean elevation of the northern part of the area is ranging from 50 m to 100 m from sea-level. Southern parts of Tlawng watershed is elevated between 400 m to 550 m from mean-sea level. Similarly, the northern part of the study area is gentle as compared to south. The entire watershed is under the direct influence of monsoon and annual rainfall of the study area is about 259 cm and winter temperature ranges from 8°C to 21°C and in summer it ranges from 20° C to 30°C (Agriculture Statistic, 2015).

Material and Methods :

Indian remote sensing satellite IRS-P6 with 23.5 m resolution and Cartosat-1 having spatial resolution 2.5 m are employed for main data mining. For assessing groundwater potential zones, 7th thematic layers, Slope, Lithology, Geological Structure, Drainage Density, Vegetation Cover, Land Use/Land Cover and Rainfall data integrated with Weighted Overlay technique using GIS platform. Survey of India Topographical map, Geological Survey of India, Google Earth and Mizoram Remote Sensing

Figure 1: Location Map of Tlawng Watershed

Application Center data has been referred in this study. Rainfall data are taken from Directorate of Agriculture, Govt. of Mizoram.

Thematic Layers :

The method and number of thematic layers used for assessing groundwater potential by RS and GIS techniques vary considerably from one study to another and their selection is arbitrary. (Machiwal et al., 2011).

Lithology :

Lithology map was prepared with the help of Geology map by Geological Survey of India (1998) map. The topographic expression of

the area often imparts fairly good indication of their lithology (GSI, 2011). Different lithological types behave differently with respect to the occurrence of hydraulic and infiltration process. Depending on their variable mineral composition that determines porosity and aquifer location. The detail knowledge of lithology provides valuable information in assessment of ground water potential (CGWB, 2007; GWREM, 2009). Lithological unit of the study area is shown in table 1 and figure 2.

Table 1 : Lithology Unit of the Study Area

Name	Area (km ²)	Per cent
Gravel, Sand and Silt	14.09	0.50
Clayey Sand	61.73	2.21
Sandstone	1799.31	64.43
Siltstone and Shale	895.11	32.05
Limestone	22.38	0.80

Geological Structure :

The most obvious structural features that are important from the ground water point of view are the lineaments (Bhatnagar & Goyal, 2012). One of the most structural features that important for ground water recharge is lineament and fault. Lineament and fracture provide the pathways for groundwater movement and provide potential for ground water recharge (Sankar, 2002). Density of lineament and fault act as a channel for ground water movement which results in increased porosity. Therefore, extension lineament and fault form productive ground water reserve. Figure 3 shown

Figure 2 : Lithology of Tlawng Watershed

Lineament/Fault density of the study area.

Slope :

In the gentle slope area, the surface runoff is slow allowing more time for rainwater to percolate, whereas, steep slope area facilitates high runoff allowing less residence time for rainwater to percolate and hence comparatively less infiltration (Patil & Mohite, 2014). The whole watershed is sloping towards south to north direction, meaning drainage lines are running south to

Table 2: Slope Degree Class of the Study Area

Degree of Slope	Area (km ²)	Per cent
>40	114.57	4.10
30-40	455.92	16.33
20-30	890.29	31.88
10-20	910.58	32.61
<10	421.25	15.08

north direction. Slope degree class of the study area is shown in table 2 and figure 4.

Drainage Density :

Drainage density is an inverse function of permeability. Drainage density can indirectly indicate the groundwater potential of an area

due to its relation to surface runoff and permeability (Hutti & Nijagunappa, 2011). Similarly, the higher drainage density is runoff is high and less infiltration, the faster the movement of surface flow. Drainage density of the study area is shown in table 2 and figure 5.

Figure 4: Slope Degree Categories of Tlawng Watershed

Land Use/Land Cover :

Impacts of LU/LC change on subsurface components of the hydrologic cycle is less well recognized, particularly groundwater recharge. The potential scale of subsurface impacts is large. The

impacts of LU/LC change on spatiotemporal variability in ground water recharge (Scanlon et al., 2005). Increased of settlement and build-up land has direct influenced on runoff capacity and amount. Changes of forest to cultivated and other purpose has direct impact on ground water recharge and ground water hydraulic.LU/LC of the Study Area is shown in table 3 and figure 6.

Table 3 : Land Use/Land Cover Classes of the Study Area

Land Use	Area (km ²)	Per cent
Settlement & Built-up Area	33.77	1.21
Mining/Quarrying	29.72	1.06
Agriculture Land	0.84	0.03
Horticulture/Plantation	12.34	0.44
Shifting Cultivation	8.18	0.29
Dense Forest	797.66	28.56
Moderate Forest	1153.68	41.31
Scrub Forest	751.31	26.90
Grass Land	4.16	0.15
Water Body	0.94	0.03

Figure 5 : Drainage Density of Tlawng Watershed

Figure 6 : Land Use/Land Cover of Tlawng Watershed

Rainfall :

The study area has been strong experienced and affected by tropical monsoon climate and rainy

seasons. Hence, it is necessary to take rainfall into account as a factor input for ground water potential zonation. Precipitation is a controlling factor of intensity of ground water recharge and ground

water level. The impact of changing rainfall intensities on groundwater recharge in the tropics is unclear (Ower et al., 2009). Substantially, distribution and intensity of precipitation has impact on the amount of ground water recharge over time and space. Average Annual Rainfall of Tlawng Watershed, 2013-14 is shown in figure 7.

Vegetation Cover :

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was calculated to enhance the spectral

difference between different objects. Vegetation cover is one of the important determinant factors for ground water recharge in the study area. Vegetation plays key roles in the interactions between groundwater and surface water systems, because of its direct and indirect influence on ground recharge. Changes in vegetation cover and structure, particularly from low vegetation such as grassland to tall vegetation such as a forest can have a significant impact on groundwater recharge. Vegetation Cover of study area is shown in figure 8.

Results and Discussion :

Integrating the determining factors by giving different rank of that thematic map was scaled by the weight of sub-theme. The final map is prepared and categorized into five ground water potential zones; (i) Very good, (ii) Good, (iii) Moderate, (iv) Low and (v) Very Poor potential zones (Fig. 9). Various classes are described as below:

Very Good :

Very Good ground water potential zone occupies 71.31 sq km(2.55 per cent) of the total area (Table 4). This zone is mainly concentrated in northern, southern and eastern part of the study area along the low laying areas with parts of flood plain and valley fills. This zone generally confined in valley fills, flood plain and low laying areas (Fig. 9). Slope condition and

nature of lithology has high degree of retaining water and percolation and maximum pore space between the grains. Lithologically, most of the areas is covered with sandstone and clayey sand. Besides, distributions of rainfall give rise to more variable ground water recharge and ground water level.

of the areas are falling 10-15 degree slope and covered with sandstone. Sandstone are generally capable of storing and transmitting water through their interstices and pore spaces present in between the grains, and are considered to be suitable aquifer (Lalbiakmawia, 2015). Although, rainfall intensity and vegetation cover has a significant impact on ground water potential in the study area.

Figure 8 : Vegetation Cover of Tlawng Watershed

Good Ground :

This zone occupied 439.02 sq km (15.72 per cent) of the study area. The low-lying areas including parts valley plains and valley fills are also included in this zone. Most

Moderate :

Moderate groundwater potential zones cover an area of 620.59 sq km which is 22.22 percent of the watershed (Table 4). This zone is running a longitudinal direction and mainly western and central part of the watershed. Moderate zone mainly concentrated areas where lithology and slope conditions are neither moderate nor poor condition for ground water yield and ground water recharge. The lithology of this zone is dominated by siltstone and shale with 20-30 degree slope which is lesser favourable for groundwater recharge and the potentiality is minimized by the sloping nature of the topography where runoff is prominent (Fig.9).

Poor Ground :

Mostly this zone is concentrated in the ridge line and high relief, meaning high degree of surface-runoff, which is a poor condition for infiltration beneath the ground surface(Fig.9). The lithology of this zone is occupied by siltstone

and shale which is poor condition infiltration. The undulating topography of the area possess high drainage density is given that rapid runoff and less infiltration process. Most of this area is covered by moderate dense forest. Hence, due to the above mention the ground water yield and ground water recharge is generally assumed as low. This zone occupies about 52 percent (1478.78 sq km) of the study area (Table 4).

Table 4 : Ground Water Potential Zones of the Study Area

Class	Area (km ²)	Per cent
Very Good	71.31	2.55
Good	439.02	15.72
Moderate	620.59	22.22
Poor	1478.78	52.95
Very Poor	182.89	6.54

Very Poor Ground :

A very small area covering hill ridge of the eastern and central part of the study area are registered under this category. This area covers about 6.5 per cent (182.89 sq km) of the study area (Table 4). Poor ground water potential zones are characterized by high relief and poor lithological condition for ground water potential. Also, characterized by high degree of slope and surrounded by wasteland and build-up area (Fig. 9).

Conclusion :

Different concepts and assessment techniques may be

Figure 9 : Ground Water Potential Zones of Tlawng Watershed

appropriate for assessment of ground water potential zones. The study proves that remote sensing data provides reliable information for ground water study. GIS technology is useful and efficient for spatial data management and manipulation. The integration and analysis of determining factors are useful for assessment of ground water potential in Tlawng watershed. The study found out that valley fills, flood plain and low laying areas have more advantages of ground water potential due to the

Table 5 : Rank and Weightage of Different Parameters for Delineating Groundwater Potential Zones

Sl. No	Layers	Weights (%)	Classes	Rank
1	Geological Structured (Lineament & Faults Density)	20	>20 per sq km	8
			15-20 per sq km	6
			10-15 per sq km	4
			5-10 per sq km	3
			<5 per sq km	2
2	Lithology	20	Gravel Sand & Silt	5
			Sandstone	8
			Clayey Sand	9
			Siltstone & Shale	2
			Limestone	2
3	Slope	15	>40 Degree	1
			30-40 Degree	3
			20-30 Degree	5
			10-20 Degree	7
			<10 Degree	8
4	Rainfall	10	>3167 mm	9
			2667-3167 mm	7
			2167-2667 mm	6
			1667-2167 mm	3
			< 1667 mm	1
5	Land Use/Land Cover (LULC)	15	Built-up	1
			Wasteland	1
			Agriculture	2
			Horticulture	3
			Shifting Cultivation	2
			Dense Forest	8
			Moderate Forest	7
			Scrub Forest	5
			Grass Land	3
Water Body	9			
6	Drainage Density	10	>4km/sq km	1
			3-4 km/sq km	3
			2-3 km/sq km	5
			1-2 km/sq km	6
			<1km/sq km	8
7	Vegetation Cover	10	Very Dens	8
			Dens	7
			Moderate	6
			Low	4
			Very Low	3
	Barren/Rocky	1		

lithology, slope and proximity of surface water helps ground water recharge. The final map prepared through the present study shows detailed idea about groundwater potentiality zones of the area. In such region groundwater needs to be augmented utilization and systematic distribution through suitable watershed management for future demand. This is an important database identifying critical areas for implementing ground development and management programme.

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